

Audio recording code for Teensy 3.2

Contact and credit

The code for the Teensy 3.2 and the attached audio shield was designed by Linus Fässler, in the framework of a MsC thesis at the University of Bern (Switzerland) and was supervised by Natalie Ceperely (University of Bern, Switzerland).

The codes are open-source.

For any questions, please contact linus_faessler@hotmail.com

Description for Teensy 3.2 & audio shield

The core of the datalogger is the Teensy 3.2 microcontroller. Together with the audio shield and the power supply unit forms the autonomous datalogger to record sounds. In general, the sensor is divided into three different components, where each fulfills specific tasks:

1. Power supply, with a voltage converter, solar panel, and lithium-polymer(LiPo) battery
2. Microcontroller with real-time clock (RTC) to keep time stamp
3. Audio shield with the connected microphone

All the used components of the Audio recording unit you can find in the following links: (Last access: 2023-01-16)

- [Teensy 3.2 \(https://www.pjrc.com/store/teensy32.html\)](https://www.pjrc.com/store/teensy32.html)
- [Audio Board for Teensy 3.0 - 3.6 \(Rev C\) \(http://www.pjrc.com/store/teensy3_audio.html\)](http://www.pjrc.com/store/teensy3_audio.html)
- [Microphone \(AOM-6738P-R-31973\) \(https://www.pjrc.com/store/microphone.html\)](https://www.pjrc.com/store/microphone.html)
- [Coin cell holder 3V CR2032 \(https://www.adafruit.com/product/1870\)](https://www.adafruit.com/product/1870)
- [RTC Quarzkristall 32.768 kHz 12.5 pF \(https://www.conrad.ch/de/p/euroquartz-quarzkristall-quarz-tc38-zyylinder-32-768-khz-12-5-pf-x-h-3-1-mm-x-8-mm-1-st-156098.html\)](https://www.conrad.ch/de/p/euroquartz-quarzkristall-quarz-tc38-zyylinder-32-768-khz-12-5-pf-x-h-3-1-mm-x-8-mm-1-st-156098.html)
- [Microphone Wind Protection \(https://www.conrad.de/de/p/monacor-ws-20-mikrofon-windschutz-durchmesser-20-mm-1332972.html\)](https://www.conrad.de/de/p/monacor-ws-20-mikrofon-windschutz-durchmesser-20-mm-1332972.html)
- [Solar Power Management Module \(https://www.maker-shop.ch/solar-power-manager-for-9v-12v-18v-solar-panel\)](https://www.maker-shop.ch/solar-power-manager-for-9v-12v-18v-solar-panel)
- [Solar Panel 18V 10W \(https://www.maker-shop.ch/polysilicon-solar-panel-18v-10w\)](https://www.maker-shop.ch/polysilicon-solar-panel-18v-10w)
- [Sensor Case PE \(https://www.distrelec.ch/de/kunststoffgehaeuse-120x200x75mm-dunkelgrau-abs-ip65-rnd-components-rnd-455-00221/p/30064442?track=true&no-cache=true&marketingPopup=\)](https://www.distrelec.ch/de/kunststoffgehaeuse-120x200x75mm-dunkelgrau-abs-ip65-rnd-components-rnd-455-00221/p/30064442?track=true&no-cache=true&marketingPopup=))
- [3.7 V LiPo 2000mAh \(https://www.distrelec.ch/de/lithium-polymer-akku-ah-mikroelektronika-mikroe-1120/p/30154716?track=true&no-cache=true&marketingPopup=false\)](https://www.distrelec.ch/de/lithium-polymer-akku-ah-mikroelektronika-mikroe-1120/p/30154716?track=true&no-cache=true&marketingPopup=false)

Manual for Teensy 3.2 & audio shield to run the Arduino code

The tutorial will guide you step by step from installing the required software on your computer, installing the required libraries and compiling the code to the audio recording unit. If you have any questions please do not hesitate to contact me.

1. Install software [Arduino IDE \(https://www.arduino.cc/en/software\)](https://www.arduino.cc/en/software) on your computer. Note: Install older version (like Arduino IDE 1.8.19) of Arduino IDE before 2.x.x
2. Install software add-on for Teensy the [Teensyduino IDE \(https://www.pjrc.com/teensy/td_download.html\)](https://www.pjrc.com/teensy/td_download.html) on your computer.
3. Install [Processing \(https://processing.org/download\)](https://processing.org/download) on your computer to set computer time on the Teensy
4. Open Teensyduino and connect the Teensy 3.2
5. Select Teensy 3.2 as a device in Teensyduino and select the used USB port
6. Install the needed libraries for the Audio recording code: ([Manual \(https://docs.simplefoc.com/library_download\)](https://docs.simplefoc.com/library_download) to install libraries in Arduino IDE from GitHub)
 - o [SD-Card read and write \(www.github.com/arduino-libraries/SD\)](http://www.github.com/arduino-libraries/SD)
 - o [Audio record and play \(www.github.com/PaulStoffregen/Audio\)](http://www.github.com/PaulStoffregen/Audio)
 - o [DeepSleep \(www.github.com/duff2013/Snooze/\)](http://www.github.com/duff2013/Snooze/)
 - o [RTC for Teensy \(www.github.com/PaulStoffregen/Time\)](http://www.github.com/PaulStoffregen/Time)
 - o [Serial Flash \(https://github.com/PaulStoffregen/SerialFlash\)](https://github.com/PaulStoffregen/SerialFlash)
 - o [elapsedMillis \(https://github.com/pfeerick/elapsedMillis\)](https://github.com/pfeerick/elapsedMillis)
7. Run [TimeTeensy3.ino \(www.github.com/PaulStoffregen/Time/tree/master/examples/TimeTeensy3\)](http://www.github.com/PaulStoffregen/Time/tree/master/examples/TimeTeensy3) example on Teensyduino IDE from the RTC for Teensy Library
8. Run [SyncArduinoClock.pde \(https://github.com/PaulStoffregen/Time/tree/master/examples/Processing/SyncArduinoClock\)](https://github.com/PaulStoffregen/Time/tree/master/examples/Processing/SyncArduinoClock) example on Processing from the RTC for Teensy Library and open the serial monitor according to the selected USB-Port to set the time by clicking with your mouse
9. Open the file "Datalogger_record_v0.8.1_fieldVersion.ino" with Teensyduino IDE and set the required time interval for your project. Then you can run the code and the Audio recording unit is set up.

Manual to convert RAW to WAV

The recorded files from the Audio recording unit are in RAW format. The Matlab code needs WAV files to perform the code. Therefore the "ConvertRawToWav.sh" converts and copies the directory with the RAW audio files into a new directory with the WAV audio files.

Note: The code runs on MAC OSX on bash terminal (LINUX), and has not been tested on windows.

1. Install [Homebrew \(https://brew.sh\)](https://brew.sh)
2. Install [SoX \(https://sox.sourceforge.net\)](https://sox.sourceforge.net) with the Homebrew by entering "\$ brew install sox*" into the terminal
3. Edit the File "ConvertRawToWav.sh" by entering the input and output directories.

4. Inserting the edited code into the terminal and run it

Manual for Lowest_median_filter.m

The entire code is designed and developed by WM. Alexandre Osborne. For reuse give credit to WM. Alexandre Osborne. If you want to understand more of the code and how it was used for in his work, see:

Osborne, W. A., Hodge, R. A., Love, G. D., Hawkin, P., & Hawkin, R. E. (2021). Babbling brook to thunderous torrent: Using sound to monitor river stage. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, 46 (13), 2656–2670. doi: 10.1002/esp.5199

1. Install Matlab (<https://mathworks.com/>).
2. Open the "Lowest_median_filter.m"
3. Enter the directory to the folder containing the audio files in WAV format
4. Run the Code
 - o You get 19 frequency bins ranging from 0.05 - 19 kHz in steps of 1000 Hz.
 - o If you use the logarithmic scale for the received values you get the dB value for each for the frequency bin